

Design of High performance MIPS-32 Pipeline Processor

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Abstract - The paper describes the design and synthesis of a basic 5 stage pipelined MIPS-32 processor for finding the longer path delay using different process technologies. The large propagation delay or critical path within the circuit and improving the hardware which causes delay is a standard method for increasing the performance. The organization of pipeline stages in such a way that pipeline can be clocked at a high frequency. The design has been synthesized at different process technologies targeting using Spartan3, Spartan6, Virtex4, Virtex5 and Virtex6 devices. The synthesis report indicates that critical path delay is located in execution unit. The maximum critical path delay is 41.405ns at 90nm technology and minimum critical path delay is 6.57ns at 40nm technology. The performance comparison result at different technologies shows that pipeline processor can work at 178MHz in 40nm technology i.e. 49.7% better than other technologies.

Keywords- MIPS Processor, Datapath, ALU, register file, pipeline

I. INTRODUCTION

The worldwide development of high end, sophisticated digital design system created a huge demand for high speed and low power general purpose processor. The performance of processor has increased exponentially since their launch in 1970. Today a high performance processor has a significant impact on the commercial market place.

Different processor architecture have developed and optimized to achieve better performance. The MIPS is known as one of the best RISC processors ever designed, and grew out of research started at Stanford University. It came in about 1987, from the MIPS project. Along with the Berkeley RISC projects, the Stanford MIPS project was one of the first publicly known implementations of the Reduced Instruction Set Computer (RISC) architecture. Among all the current RISC architectures, MIPS remain as one of the simplest. This simplicity makes the MIPS architectures a favorite choice among universities and research labs for using as the base of their design. This simplicity also makes the MIPS architecture very attractive to the embedded microprocessor market as it enables very cost-effective implementations.

A. PROCESSOR OVERVIEW

A MIPS-based RISC processor was introduced in [1], is

described. For describing the processor architecture, a basic model is chosen. Fig. 1.1 represents the top-level schematic of the MIPS pipelined processor. This schematic shows the principal components, or main blocks of the processor. It was a fixed-point processor and consist five stages, i.e. fetch, decode, execute, memory access, and write back. The MIPS architecture is included 47 instructions. The register file has thirty two 32-bit registers. This processor has a 32-bit address bus and a 32-bit data bus. The most important feature for evaluating a design is maximum attainable frequency. It can be found by detecting the longest delay or critical path within the different stages of the processor. In this design the critical path was located in ALU stage or execution stage.

Fig. 1.1 Top level schematic of MIPS pipelined processor

The aim of this paper is to design and synthesis a pipelined MIPS 32-bit processor at different process technology and their performance analysis.

This paper is organized as follows. The related work describes as brief in Section II. The pipeline stages of MIPS are explained in Section III. Different part of pipeline stages of MIPS in detail with corresponding diagrams in various sub-sections. The simulation results of pipeline stages with corresponding sub-modules are shown in section IV. Verification and synthesis report are describes in section V. The conclusions of paper are described in section VI. The future scope of the paper is shown in section VII.

B. MIPS INSTRUCTION SET

MIPS design was intended to simplify processor design by eliminating hardware interlocks between the pipeline stages. A MIPS processor consists of an integer processing unit and a collection of coprocessors that perform ancillary tasks or operate on other types of data [3]. Like other RISC designs, the MIPS instruction set is straightforward. MIPS are a load/store architecture, which means that only load and store instructions access memory. Other instructions can only operate on values in registers [2-5]. Generally, the MIPS instructions can be broken into three classes: the memory-reference instructions, the arithmetic- logical instructions, and the branch instructions. Also, there are three different instructions formats in MIPS architecture: R-Type instructions, I-Type instructions, and J-Type instructions as shown in Fig. 1.2. The MIPS instruction field is described in Table 1.1.

Fig. 1.2 MIPS Instruction Types

Field	Description
<i>Op</i> [31-26]	is a 6-bit operation code
<i>RS</i> [25-21]	is a 5-bit source register specifier
<i>RT</i> [20-16]	is a 5-bit target(source/destination) register or branch condition
<i>Immediate</i> [15-0]	is a 16-bit immediate, branch displacement or address displacement
<i>Target</i> [25-0]	is a 26-bit jump target address
<i>RD</i> [15-11]	is a 5-bit destination register specifier
<i>Shamt</i> [10-6]	is a 5-bit shift amount
<i>Funct</i> [5-0]	is a 6-bit function field

Table 1.1 MIPS Instruction Fields

II. RELATED WORK

There has been a lot of previous research work on improving the performance of pipeline RISC based processor. **XiangYunZhu et.al** in this paper, MIPS instruction format, decoder module function and design theory for RISC processor is analyzed. **Mamun Bin Ibne Reaz et.al** this paper describes a design methodology of a single clock cycle MIPS RISC Processor using VHDL to ease the description, verification, simulation and hardware realization. **Shofiquil Islam et.al** this paper describes a design of High-Speed-Pipelined Execution Unit of 32-bit RISC Processor using verilog HDL.

III. PIPELINE DESIGN

The pipeline structure of the processor is a modified version of a popular load/store RISC [4]. The basic pipeline for a MIPS integer unit contains 5 stages: Instruction fetch (IF), Instruction decode (ID), Execution (EX), Memory access (MEM), and Write back (WB). The five stages of the pipeline can operate concurrently, using synchronization signals: Clock and Reset. MIPS instruction fetch and MIPS instruction execution is very high performance because of three types format with given length. Several simple MIPS instruction can accomplish complicated operations by compiler [8].

A. Instruction fetch unit

The function of the instruction fetch unit is to obtain an instruction from the instruction memory using the current value of the PC and increment the PC value for the next instruction as shown in Fig 3.1.

Since this design uses an 8-bit data width we had to implement byte addressing to access the registers and word address to access the instruction memory. The instruction fetch component contains the following logic elements that are implemented in VHDL: 8-bit program counter (PC) register, an adder to increment the PC by four, the instruction memory, a multiplexor, and an AND gate used to select the value of the next PC.

Fig. 3.1. MIPS Instruction Fetch Unit

B. Instruction Decode and Write back unit

The main function of the instruction decode unit is to use the 32-bit instruction provided from the previous instruction fetch unit to index the register file and obtain the register data values as seen in Fig. 3.2. This unit also sign extends instruction bits [15 - 0] to 32-bit. However with our design of 8-bit data width, our implementation uses the instruction bits [7 - 0] bits instead of sign extending the value. The logic elements include several multiplexors and the register file. The Write Back stage is where any calculated values are written back to their proper registers.

Fig. 3.2. MIPS Instruction Decode Unit

C. Execution unit

The execution unit of the MIPS processor contains the arithmetic logic unit (ALU) which performs the operation determined by the ALUop signal. The branch address is calculated by adding the PC+4 to the sign extended immediate field shifted left 2 bits by a separate adder. The logic elements to be implemented in VHDL include a multiplexor, an adder, the ALU and the ALU control as shown in Fig 3.3.

Fig. 3.3. MIPS execution unit

D. Memory access unit

The data memory unit is only accessed by the load and store instructions. The load instruction asserts the MemRead signal and uses the ALU Result value as an address to index the data memory. The read output data is then subsequently written into the register file. A store instruction asserts the MemWrite signal and writes the data value previously read from a register into the computed memory address. Fig 3.4 shows the signals used by the memory unit.

Fig. 3.4. MIPS Data Memory Unit

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

Different capabilities and features of VHDL lead to various implementation of the design in terms of performance and speed. Xilinx 12.3 software is used as synthesis tool and Xilinx ISIM is used as simulation tool.

A. . Instructions fetch stage

The Instruction Fetch (IF) stage fetches the instruction according to Program Counter address. The instruction fetch entity (inst_fetch) includes the following components: PC register (PC_REG), PC selector Mux (MUX), Instruction Memory (InstMEM), and PC Adder (hybrid_adder).

Fig 4.1 shows the simulation result of the IF entity. As seen in the results, after InstRead is set, instruction is fetched from the branch instruction address again and the PC counter is incremented by 4, where the instructions are fetched from instruction memory. Fig. 4.2 and Table 4.1 shows the RTL structure and signal definition used in the instruction fetch stage.

Fig. 4.1. Simulation results of instruction fetch

Fig. 4.2. RTL view of instruction fetch stage

Signal	Function
<i>PC_in</i> [31-0]	Input of program counter
<i>CLK2</i>	Input to Instruction memory Clock signal
<i>PC_out</i> [31-0]	Output of program counter
<i>Inst_in</i> [31-0]	(32-bit) instruction
<i>Inst_address</i> [31-0]	Instruction address
<i>PC_out</i> [31-0]	Read address from PC
<i>CLK1</i>	Input to Program counter Clock signal
<i>InstLoad</i>	Enable/disable write signal
<i>InstRead</i>	Enable/disable read signal
<i>Inst_out</i> [31-0]	Instruction data output
<i>Pc_out</i> [31-0]	Instruction address input
<i>add_next_out</i> [31-0]	prepare PC+4 for next instruction fetch
<i>Add_brn_out</i> [31-0]	Branch address input
<i>PC_sel_br</i>	Select branch address
<i>mux_pcb_r_out</i> [31-0]	Mux branch selected output
<i>busA</i> [31-0]	Jump address input
<i>PC_sel_jmp</i>	Select jump address

Table 4.1. Signal definitions of instruction fetch entity

B. Instruction decode and write back stage

The Instruction Decode (ID) stage decodes the machine code bits given to it by the IF stage. The Write Back (WB) stage writes the results from load and ALU instructions back to the register file. These two stages are combined into one entity because the register file is shared between the two stages. The ID/WB entity (*inst_decode*) contains the following components: integer register file (REGfile), sign extended module (extender), instruction decoder module (Instructiondecoder), and mux unit (MUX_5bit). Fig 4.3 and Fig 4.4 shows the simulation results of the ID/WB stage. As the results shows, the register file is read by the falling edge of the clock signal, and written with write signal.

Fig 4.5 and Table 4.2 show the RTL structure and signal definition are used in the instruction decode stage.

Fig. 4.4. Simulation result of write back stage

Signal	Function
<i>busW</i> [31-0]	Input write data to register file
<i>Inst_out</i> [31-0]	32-bit register instruction data output signal to register file
<i>CLK3</i>	Input clock signal to register file
<i>RegWr</i>	Input Register write control signal
<i>ExtOp</i>	Input Sign extender control signal
<i>RegDst</i>	Input Register destination control signal input
<i>busA</i> [31-0]	Read data 1 output from register file
<i>busB</i> [31-0]	Read data 2 output from register file
<i>ext_out</i> [31-0]	Extender output
<i>RS</i> [4-0]	First register for source operand
<i>RT</i> [4-0]	Second register for source operand
<i>RD</i> [4-0]	Register for destination operand
<i>Rd_rf</i> [4-0]	Mux RD output signal
<i>Iaddress</i> [15-0]	Immediate addressing signal

Table 4.2. Signal definition of instruction decode entity

Fig. 4.5. RTL view of decode stage

C. Execution stage

The Execution stage (EX), executes the given instruction according to the ALU control signal. Figure 4.6 shows the simulation result of the execution stage. The execution entity (*execution_unit*) contains arithmetic logic unit (ALU), shift left 2 register (shift2) Mux (MUX and MUX_5bit), ALU control (*alu_control*), adder (*hybrid_adder*).

Fig. 4.3. Simulation result of decode stage

Fig. 4.7 and Table 4.3 shows the RTL structure and signal definitions are used in the execution stage.

Fig. 4.6. Simulation result of execution stage

Fig. 4.7. RTL view of execution stage

signal	Function
<i>busA[31-0]</i>	Input to ALU
<i>busB[31-0]</i>	Input to MUX asserted when low
<i>ext_out[31-0]</i>	Input to MUX asserted when high and input to shf lft2 unit
<i>add_next_out[31-0]</i>	Input to hybrid_adder unit
<i>Inst_out[10-6]</i>	Input to mux_5bit asserted when low
<i>Alu_op[2-0]</i>	ALU operation input to alu_control unit
<i>func[5-0]</i>	ALU operation function
<i>shfCtrl</i>	Control signal to mux_5bit
<i>ALUSrc</i>	Control signal to MUX
<i>add_brn_out[31-0]</i>	Output of hybrid_adder unit
<i>ALU_out[31-0]</i>	Output of ALU unit
<i>jump</i>	Output of alu_control
<i>Equal</i>	Output of ALU unit

Table 4.3. Signal definition of execution unit

D. Memory access stage

The Memory stage (MEM) reads and writes results to and from the data memory (MEM) and Executes the branch control. Fig. 4.8 shows the simulation result of the Memory Access stage.

Fig. 4.9 and Table 4.4 shows the RTL structure and signal definition are used in memory access stage.

Fig. 4.8. Simulation result of memory access stage

Fig. 4.9. Entity structure of memory access stage

Signal	Function
<i>busB[31-0]</i>	input data to DataMEM
<i>ALU_out[31-0]</i>	input address to DataMEM
<i>CLK4</i>	Input clock signal to DataMEM
<i>MemWr</i>	input write signal to DataMEM
<i>MemRead</i>	Input read signal to DataMEM
<i>Data_out[31-0]</i>	Output data from DataMEM

Table 4.4. Signal definition of memory access unit

V. VERIFICATION AND SYNTHESIS

The complete pipeline processor stages are modelled in VHDL. The syntax of the RTL design is checked using Xilinx tool. For functional verification of the design the MIPS processor is modelled in Hardware descriptive language. The design is verified both at a block level and top level. Test cases for the block level are generated in VHDL by both directed and random way. Table 5.1 shows the corresponding symbol and an architectural body in the RTL view. For top level verification assembly program are written and the corresponding hex code from the assembler is fed to both RTL design and model the checker module captures and compares the signal from both the model and display the message form mismatching of digital values.

The complete design along with all timing constraints, area utilization and optimization options are described using synthesis report. The MIPS design is synthesized at different technology as Spartan-3, Spartan-6, Virtex-4, Virtex-5 and

Virtex-6 at 90nm, 45nm, 90nm, 65nm and 40nm. In all of these devices Virtex-6 has higher performance than others.

Stage	Subunits
IF	INST_MEM, PC, Add_next, mux_pcbr, mux_pcjmp
ID	Ins_decdd, mux_rw, extend, reg_file
EXE	Mux_shf, shf_lf_2, Add_brn, mux_alu, ALUnit, v0
MEM	Data_MEM
WB	Mux_busW

Table 5.1 The subunits used in the different stages of the processor

The design has been synthesized targeting 40nm triple oxide process technology using Xilinx Virtex-6 (xc6vlx240t-3ff1156), 65nm triple oxide process technology using Virtex-5 (xc5vlx220-2ff1760), 90nm triple oxide process technology using Virtex-4 (xc4vlx200-11ff1513), 45nm 9metal, dual oxide process technology using Spartan6 (xc6slx150-3fgg676), 90nm dual oxide process technology using Spartan3 (xc3s200-5ft256) device. The Virtex family is the latest and fastest FPGA which aims to provide up to 15% lower dynamic and static power and 15% improved performance than the previous generation. It is obvious that there is a trade-off between maximum clock frequency and area utilization (number of slices LUT's) because the basic programmable part of FPGA is the slice that contain four LUTs (look up table) and eight Flip flops. Some of the slice can use their LUT's as distributed RAM.

A. AREA UTILIZATION ANALYSIS

The area utilization summary of the pipeline stage is briefly shown in Table 5.1. The area synthesis report shows that with the decrease of process technology from 90nm to 40nm the area increase. The graphical representation of the area utilization is shown in Fig. 5.1. At 40nm and 45nm technology the area is approximately twice than others technologies.

Module	Area utilization				
	Spartan3	Spartan6	Virtex4	Virtex5	Virtex6
Technology	90nm	45nm	90nm	65nm	40nm
IF	13860	33083	13852	19925	33067
ID	126	55	298	55	55
EXE	333	421	334	461	419
MEM	13678	32885	13677	19784	32888
WB	18	32	18	32	32

Table 5.2 Area utilization summary

Fig. 5.1 Graphical representation shows area utilize at each pipeline stage

B. PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

In the processor, the design clock cycle was determined by calculating each element delay using the timing information summary in the Xilinx. The performance report of the pipeline stage with respect to different technology as shown in Table 5.3. the critical path delay occurs at execution stage of pipeline processor. The longest delay inside the execution stage is 19.612ns at 45nm which is reduced to 6.5ns at 40nm technology and operation frequency is 51MHz to 152MHz. Fig5.2 shows the graphical representation of Performance comparison between different stages of pipeline at different technologies. The complete pipeline stages datapath including IF, ID, EXE, MEM, WB the longest delay inside the processor is reduced from 9.102ns at 45nm to 2.102ns at 40nm process technology. This value improves operation frequency from 109.8MHz to 475.7MHz.

MIPS instruction fetch (IF) and MIPS execution (EXE) shows very high performance because of three type's instruction format with given length. Each stage of pipeline is linearly increased with the decrease of process technology.

Module	Max. attainable Frequency (MHz)				
	Spartan3	Spartan6	Virtex4	Virtex5	Virtex6
Technology	90nm	45nm	90nm	65nm	40nm
IF	117	237	347	377	556
ID	102	170	153	264	1062
EXE	24	51	42	91	152
MEM	471	59	1038	1024	218
WB	116	159	166	255	1139

Table 5.3 Performance analysis report

Fig. 5.2 Graphical representation shows the performance comparison between different technology

VI. CONCLUSION

MIPS processor is widely used RISC processor in industry and research area. In this paper, we have successfully designed and synthesized a basic model of pipelined MIPS processor. The design has been modeled in VHDL and functional verification policies adopted for it. Synthesis of the design is carried out Spartan3, Virtex-6, Virtex-5, Virtex-4, and Spartan6 family devices at 90nm, 40nm, 65nm, and 90nm and 45nm process technology. The simulation results show that maximum frequency in execution unit is increased from 51MHz at 45nm to 152 MHz at 40nm technology. The synthesis report indicates that each stage of pipeline in virtex-6 device is clocked at higher clock frequency. So, this concludes that Virtex-6 device has high speed and high performance FPGA device than others. The complete processor design including pipeline stages is working at 178MHz frequency after synthesis at 40nm technology i.e. maximum of 49.7% better than other technologies.

VII. FUTURE WORK

This paper presents a comparative performance analysis and finding longer path delay at different pipeline stages using different technologies device. Our future work includes changing the processor architecture to make it capable of handling multiple threads and supporting network security application more effectively.

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